

EXPERIENCE OF FOREIGN COUNTRIES IN REVIEWING APPEALS FROM INDIVIDUALS AND LEGAL ENTITIES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the experience of foreign countries in reviewing appeals from individuals and legal entities from both scientific-theoretical and practical perspectives. Specifically, the legal mechanisms and administrative procedures for receiving, registering, reviewing, and responding to appeals were studied in developed countries such as European Union member states, the USA, Germany, France, South Korea, and Japan. Additionally, effective methods aimed at utilizing digital technologies in this field, electronic appeal systems, ensuring openness and transparency, and protecting the rights of appellants were analyzed. Based on the research results, proposals and conclusions are presented regarding the implementation of advanced foreign practices into national legislation, increasing the effectiveness of handling appeals, and strengthening citizens' trust in the activities of state bodies.

Keywords: individuals and legal entities, appeals, foreign experience, administrative procedures, electronic appeal, transparency, state bodies, legal mechanisms.

At the initiative of our President, a mechanism for identifying citizens' problems through mobile receptions and door-to-door visits has been introduced, which is not encountered in the experience of any developed countries that proclaim "human rights." Humanity, equality, and the fact that even the appeal of an ordinary citizen is constantly considered is proof that the principle of the primacy of human rights is practically ensured in Uzbekistan.

In his report on December 3, 2025, on the work aimed at increasing the effectiveness of communication between government agencies and the population, the President emphasized that "Listening to citizens must be the main criterion in the activities of government agencies."

The right of citizens to appeal is enshrined in the constitutions of most foreign states. In Germany, Great Britain, and Australia, the right of citizens to appeal to state bodies is considered as a mechanism for monitoring and controlling the state's parliamentary and legislative activities and is considered a separate part of the activities of legislative and executive bodies. The procedure and processes for reviewing appeals are also different. For example:

Article 29 of the Spanish Constitution stipulates that all Spaniards have the right to submit individual and collective written appeals to state bodies in the form and for the purposes established by law.

Article 28 of the Constitution of Belgium, entitled "Belgians and their rights," establishes the right of every person to apply to the state authorities with an application (petition) signed by one or more persons.

Article 45 of the Bulgarian Constitution stipulates that citizens have the right to appeal to state bodies with complaints, proposals, and applications.

The Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On the Consideration of Appeals of Individuals and Legal Entities"[1] establishes the types of appeals in the form of an official request and a response. In accordance with the law, an official request is a person's request to provide information of a personal or social nature, and a response is a person's expression of their attitude to the domestic and foreign policy pursued by the state, as well as to events and phenomena of a social nature.

Unlike national legislation, in Italy, a state fee is levied on complaints and other actions related to their consideration. Exemption from duty or reduction of its amount is allowed only by a reasoned decision of the court considering the complaint.

Finnish law establishes specific requirements for the form of appeal to the administrative body, its delivery, and registration. Documents submitted to government bodies must state the merits of the case. It must also indicate the name of the applicant and the contact details necessary for resolving the case. The document is considered received, accepted by this authority from the date of its receipt by the authority. A document sent by mail is considered received from the moment it arrives at the official mailbox of the authority or from the moment this authority receives notification from the postal company about the receipt of the postal item.

In accordance with the Czech Constitution, the application of a legal entity must indicate an identification number and the address of registration in the register of the enterprise or any other register established by law[3].

In Lithuania, the acceptance of an appeal is confirmed by a specific document indicating the date of acceptance, the name, surname, telephone number of the official, civil servant, or employee who accepted the appeal, and the registration number of the appeal. A document confirming the acceptance of the complaint is submitted to the person or sent by mail or by e-mail. It is noteworthy that it is in this law that the norm is enshrined that a state authority is obliged to establish at least two additional hours per week after the end of the working day of this body for the acceptance of petitions and complaints. Such an approach undoubtedly takes into account the interests of workers and other employed applicants.

Also, foreign regulatory documents pay great attention to determining the departmental affiliation when filing complaints. In England, the majority of complaints are considered by special collegial bodies in ministries and departments, often in administrative tribunals, operating under quasi-judicial procedures.

According to current legislation in the United States, complaints are filed with the body to which the document or action is the subject of the complaint. Special complaint processing services will be created for the consideration of complaints within the framework of ministries and agencies. When filing complaints addressed to the head of the department, the head of the department sends them for consideration to the relevant department or an authorized official. The procedure for the activities of special services for the consideration of complaints is regulated by acts enshrining the structure of governing bodies or is determined directly by the head of the agency. Special services for the consideration of complaints are created in large municipalities, as well as in local sectoral management bodies.

Complaints regarding the actions of governing bodies and officials may be addressed to the president of the United States of America, members of Congress, or to the legislative bodies of the states. The actions of individual governing bodies and officials can be appealed to special bodies, commonly referred to in American literature as "thirbunals." Such a procedure for

considering complaints is established in relation to decisions made at the federal level by the following bodies: the Veterans' Affairs Administration, the Customs Duty Bureau, the Immigration Service, the Internal Revenue Service, and others.

In China, officials are held not only disciplinarily and administratively, but also criminally liable for violating the procedure for considering appeals.

In Japan, due to the specific mentality, preference is given not to control by law enforcement agencies (prosecutor's offices, courts), but to administrative control itself, which has its own "internal," peculiar reconciliation procedures.

Consequently, in foreign countries, appeals are considered mainly within the framework of administrative justice.

In foreign countries, the issue of confirming the identity of the author of the appeal, including the electronic appeal, is resolved differently. The legislation of most countries does not provide for the identification of individuals using an electronic digital signature (EDS) when applying.

In accordance with paragraph 3 of Article 7 of the Federal Law of the Russian Federation "On the Procedure for Considering Appeals of Citizens of the Russian Federation"[4] of 2006, "applications received by a state body, local self-government bodies, or officials in the form of an electronic document are considered in the manner prescribed by this Federal Law. In the appeal, the citizen must indicate their last name, first name, patronymic, email address, and if the response must be sent in the form of an electronic document, the postal address. A citizen has the right to attach the necessary documents and materials to such an appeal in electronic form or to send the specified documents or their copies in writing. According to the law, a response to an appeal received in the form of an electronic document is sent to the email address indicated in the appeal. In cases where the appeal does not indicate the surname of the citizen who sent the appeal, or the postal address to which the response should be sent, the appeal is not answered.

Article 25 of the Law of the Republic of Belarus "On Appeals of Citizens and Legal Entities"[5] of 2011 establishes specific requirements for electronic appeals. Requirements for special sections of the Internet intended for the placement of electronic appeals on the official websites of state bodies and representatives of other states are established by the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Belarus.

The Law of the Kyrgyz Republic "On the Procedure for Considering Citizens' Appeals" of February 26, 2008,[6] distinguishes between individual appeals, i.e., appeals of one citizen and collective appeals, appeals of two or more citizens, appeals of organizations on behalf of citizens, as well as resolutions of rallies and meetings, along with applications, proposals, and complaints. Appeals of legal entities are not regulated by law. At the same time, it is necessary to pay attention to the definition of a repeated appeal, i.e., "repeated appeals without citing new evidence or newly discovered circumstances are not considered if there are completed materials of the investigation on them and citizens have been given a response in the manner prescribed by this Law." New evidence or reopened circumstances are considered in the manner prescribed by this Law." In practice, such a situation is natural.

The experience of Estonia, where the system of working with appeals has been brought to the highest level based on information and communication technologies (ICT), is of particular interest. Estonia has begun implementing ICT, and today 90% of the country is open online. For

example, through the Unified Portal of Public Services, it is possible to obtain social security, participate in elections, apply for registration of institutions, obtain a driver's license, register a child's birth, and many other useful tasks, saving time and money.

Another direction developed abroad is the practice of submitting petitions, that is, collective appeals. For example, in the USA, the White House website has an "online petitions" section, where anyone can send their appeal to the Presidential Administration. If more than 25,000 signatures are collected on the petition, the "White House" is obliged to give an official response to the citizens' demand. If an electronic petition in the USA gathers more than 100,000 signatures, it must be considered by the President of the country. The petition must collect 150 votes within 30 days for inclusion on the site[7].

Taking this experience into account, it would be advisable to propose further improvement of the procedure for electronic petitions, that is, collective appeals via the Internet. In petitions, the population will have the opportunity to express their opinions and initiatives on issues they consider relevant. Of course, such petitions are formed through a special platform, where signatures of citizens in support are collected, and when they reach a certain number, the official petition acquires the status of a collective appeal and is mandatory for consideration by the relevant state body.

In the Republic of Korea, the "e-People" online portal for citizens' appeals, established in 2005, operates. It unites 910 state institutions. In 2015 alone, this system received and processed more than 2 million appeals. On this site, not only statistical, but also analytical information on citizens' appeals is posted on an ongoing basis.

In our opinion, it would be useful to apply this practice in Uzbekistan on the website of the Single Portal of Interactive Public Services.

In conclusion, it can be said that when studying foreign experience, you will not find the new model of "People's Reception Offices" for working with appeals from individuals and legal entities in the experience of any foreign country. It would not be an exaggeration to recognize public reception offices as a new institution in the world. It is the People's Reception Offices that embody the foundations of our national statehood, national customs and traditions, which are unique in the world. When considering the experience of foreign countries, it can be seen that a state fee is charged for appeals, or a certain number of signatures are required for the consideration of collective appeals, citizens visit government bodies with justified appeals on specific days for appeals, and a special procedure is established for the consideration of appeals from legal entities. Our Eastern system, while rejecting such restrictions, is noteworthy for being based on the principle that, as established in our fundamental law, every citizen, whether by themselves or with others, can apply to state administration bodies at any time, no fee is charged for considering appeals, and appeals from individuals and legal entities are considered in the same manner.

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